

Geometric calibration model for the 1M Astrometric GIS demonstration

prepared by: L. Lindegren
approved by:
reference: GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-063-02
issue: 2
revision: 1
date: 2008-07-22
status: Issued

Abstract

This note describes the calibration model to be used for the 1 million star Astrometric GIS demonstration. In the first issue of the note, only the purely geometric calibration was considered (no chromaticity or CTI effects). In this second issue, the magnitude and spectrum dependent calibrations are also considered, and a method to take into account their correlations with the geometric large-scale calibration is described. The method is however not easily extended to handle more general situations, and will be superseded by the generic calibration model.

Document History

Issue	Revision	Date	Author	Comment
2	1	2008-07-22	LL	Comments by Bastian taken into account
2	0	2008-07-13	LL	Magnitude and spectrum dependent calibration added
1	0	2005-11-07	LL	Only purely geometric calibration

Note: For reasons of consistency, Sections 1–3 remain unchanged from Issue 1, while Sections 4–6 were added in Issue 2. The Appendix is also unchanged from Issue 1, except that (36) was corrected.

1 Introduction

A run of the Astrometric GIS comprising up to 1 million stars is planned at ESAC as a first test of new processing concepts for Gaia. The run will iterate source updating (S), attitude updating (A) and calibration updating (C). For S and A, existing algorithms will be used, based on respectively GAIA-LL-055 and SAG-LL-037, while new code will be written for the calibration. The present note describes the proposed model and algorithm for the calibration updating. It is based on the one described in Appendix A of GAIA-LL-044 (V.4), but updated, corrected, simplified and adapted to the new source updating (re-using residuals).

The geometric calibration is concerned with modelling the centroid position (along and across scan) as function of time, field of view (Astro-1 or Astro-2), position within the field, spectral composition of the source, and other variables of relevance e.g. for CTI effects. The present model is purely geometric, neglecting the spectral dependence (chromaticity) and CTI effects.

A constraint for the model comes from the number of stars in the Astrometric GIS (of order 1 million for the present run). This limits the time scale on which the calibration can be carried out, depending on the spatial scale. For example, with a total of 10^6 primary sources, the mean rate at which the star images hit an astrometric CCD is about 5000 per day. This gives sufficient data to calibrate the bulk position of each CCD on a time scale as short as days, if required. But if we look at the small-scale calibration, typically carried out for individual pixel columns in the across-scan (AC) direction, the mean rate is only 2.5 sources per day. That calibration therefore cannot be carried out on a shorter time scale than several months.¹

The need to carry out calibrations on different spatial and temporal scales has led to the notion of ‘calibration units’. A calibration unit is a set of calibration parameters valid in a certain time interval and considered to be constant in that interval. The same set of parameters in another time interval would constitute a different calibration unit. The advantage of this concept is that each calibration unit in principle can be processed independently of the others. In the currently foreseen processing scheme, where all the astrometric calibrations could be made in parallel, this may no longer be an advantage, and the concept may eventually be abandoned.² However, in the present model we retain the discrete calibration units as a reasonable first approximation, because of its algorithmic simplicity. As in earlier notes the calibration units can be sequentially indexed (k was used for large-scale units and κ for small-scale units), but for clarity we use here instead a combination of indices for the time interval, field of view, CCD chip and pixel column, which is more directly tied to how the algorithm must be coded.

¹The ability to monitor possible instrument changes on small spatial scales is a main reason for having as many primary sources as possible in the Astrometric GIS.

²Indeed, the temporal evolution of many calibration variables could now easily, and more realistically, be modelled as continuous functions of time.

2 Geometric calibration model

The geometric model maps CCD coordinates (pixels) onto field angles (η, ζ) depending on time and FOV. The aim is to have a reasonably realistic instrument model in terms of the number of parameters to be determined, if not in terms of the actual model complexity. In particular, it is assumed that each pixel column (1966 per CCD) needs to be calibrated geometrically. The following indexing conventions will be used:

- ℓ identifies the observation (the transit of one source across a single CCD chip)
- i identifies the source
- f identifies the FOV (Astro-1 or Astro-2)
- n identifies the CCD chip
- m identifies the pixel column on the chip
- j identifies a ‘short’ calibration time interval (e.g., one month)
- k identifies a ‘long’ calibration time interval (e.g., the whole mission)

The indices i, f, n, m, j and k are assumed to be known for every observation (ℓ).

The *nominal* geometric calibration is given by the nominal along-scan coordinate η_n^0 associated with each CCD chip (both for ASM and AF), together with the nominal basic angle, and the nominal across-scan coordinate ζ_n^0 of each ASM chip. These nominal values are never changed. The *actual* calibration is expressed as small corrections to these nominal angles. In the present model, all geometric calibration parameters are expressed in radians.

2.1 Calibration parameters

We consider three kinds of calibration parameters (cf. Table 1):

1. Large-scale, along-scan geometric correction, $\Delta\eta$. There is one such value for each CCD in the ASM and AF fields. Moreover, the values are in general different in Astro-1 and Astro-2 (for the same CCD) due to optical distortion. The values are assumed to be constant only on a short time scale (1 month). $\Delta\eta$ thus depends on indices f, n and j .
2. Small-scale, along-scan geometric correction, $\delta\eta$. There is one such value for each pixel column and CCD. For a given CCD and pixel column, however, the same value applies in Astro-1 and Astro-2, since its physical origin is assumed to be on the CCD chip itself. The values are also assumed to be constant on a long time scale (whole mission). $\delta\eta$ thus depends on indices n, m and k .
3. Large-scale, across-scan geometric correction, $\Delta\zeta$. There is one value per CCD in the ASM area, and different values apply in each field. (Actually, the two fields use different CCDs.) Although the physical origin is the same as that of $\Delta\eta$, the across-scan component

TABLE 1: Summary of Astro calibration parameters for the proposed model. Small-scale parameters are defined per pixel column; large-scale parameters per CCD. Short and long time scales are of order 1 month and several years (whole mission), respectively.

Parameter		Applies to	FOV dependent	Spatial scale	Temporal scale
along-scan CCD pos.	$\Delta\eta$	ASM, AF	yes	large	short
along-scan column pos.	$\delta\eta$	ASM, AF	no	small	long
across-scan CCD pos.	$\Delta\zeta$	ASM	yes	large	long

is assumed to be constant on a long time scale, since the calibration requirement is much relaxed in the across-scan direction. $\Delta\zeta$ thus depends on f , n and k .

In summary, the field angles for any observation ℓ are modelled as:

$$\eta_\ell = \eta_n^0 + \Delta\eta_{fnj} + \delta\eta_{nmk} \quad (1a)$$

$$\zeta_\ell = \zeta_n^0 + \Delta\zeta_{fnk} \quad (1b)$$

where, for brevity, we write f instead of $f(\ell)$, and similarly for n , m , j , and k .

2.2 Constraints

In order to render all geometric calibration parameters uniquely determinable, the following constraints must be rigorously enforced by the solution:

$$\langle \Delta\eta_{fnj} \rangle_j = 0 \quad (\text{for all } j) \quad (2a)$$

$$\langle \delta\eta_{nmk} \rangle_{nk} = 0 \quad (\text{for all } n, k) \quad (2b)$$

$$\langle \Delta\zeta_{fnk} \rangle_{fk} = 0 \quad (\text{for all } f, k) \quad (2c)$$

Here, we use for brevity a shorthand notation for the averages, so that for example $\langle X_{abc} \rangle_{ab}$ is the unweighted mean of X_{abc} over the whole applicable range of the index c ; note that this average then depends on indices a and b . It is important to realize that the $\langle \rangle$ denote mean values of the *parameters*, not of the *observations* (or residuals). To be very precise, for any j ,

$$\langle \Delta\eta_{fnj} \rangle_j = \frac{\sum_f \sum_n \Delta\eta_{fnj}}{\sum_f \sum_n 1} \quad (3)$$

where the sums are taken over all values of f and n for which $\Delta\eta_{fnj}$ applies; similarly, for any combination of n and k ,

$$\langle \delta\eta_{nmk} \rangle_{nk} = \frac{\sum_m \delta\eta_{nmk}}{\sum_m 1} \quad (4)$$

where the sums are taken over all values of m for which $\delta\eta_{mkk}$ applies; finally, for any combination of f and k ,

$$\langle \Delta\zeta_{fkk} \rangle_{fk} = \frac{\sum_n \Delta\zeta_{fkn}}{\sum_n 1} \quad (5)$$

where the sums are taken over all values of n for which $\Delta\zeta_{fkn}$ applies (note that these are then not the same n values as in Eq. 3). The rationale for these constraints is as follows.

Constraint (2a) effectively defines the origin of the along-scan field angle to be that given *in the mean* by the nominal CCD positions η_n^0 . It is averaged both over n and f because the origin is not fixed separately in Astro-1 and Astro-2, but by the \mathbf{X} axis half-way between, together with the nominal basic angle used to calculate the field angles (function F below). Any deviation of the real basic angle from the nominal value used by F will show up as a systematic offset of Δ_{fnj} depending on f . There must, furthermore, be a separate constraint for each time interval j , otherwise it would not be possible to determine this calibration component as function of time.

Constraint (2b) says that, in every CCD and long time interval, the mean small-scale correction is zero, so that the mean CCD position is indeed given by Δ_{fnj} . This constraint is necessary in order to uniquely separate the large-scale from the small-scale calibrations.

Constraint (2c) defines the origin of the ζ coordinate in each field from the mean nominal positions ζ_n^0 . There must be a separate constraint for each f , since the definition of the instrument orientation about the \mathbf{X} axis is set by the origin of ζ in both fields.

2.3 Observation equations

The calibration is based on a least-squares processing of the observation equations. The basic quantity to consider is the residual of the observation equation, defined in the sense ‘observed minus calculated’ (see Appendix for some relevant least-squares terminology). However, it is not self-evident what constitutes the ‘observed’ and ‘calculated’ quantities in case of the along-scan astrometric observations. Thus it is important to explain the adopted conventions clearly.

An elementary ASM observation (ℓ) gives the time of observation t_ℓ^{obs} when the light centroid was transferred to the serial register, and the transverse pixel coordinate μ_ℓ of the centroid (where μ is a continuous version of m ; cf. Bastian BAS-003). In addition, the associated indices f , n and k are assumed to be known. Similarly, an elementary AF observation gives the time of observation t_ℓ^{obs} when the light centroid was transferred to the serial register, but in this case no across-scan coordinate was measured. However, we assume that the (approximate) pixel column m of the observation is known, or can be computed, together with the other associated indices f , n , j and k .

We use the convention that the observation equations are formulated in the field angles (η, ζ) ,

rather than, for example, in the observed CCD transit time and transverse pixel coordinate. There are several advantages to this approach. First of all, it is conceptually easier to think of positional measurements, and their associated residuals and uncertainties, in terms of angles rather than time. Second, it provides better consistency between along- and across-scan measurements, if both are expressed as angles rather than one in time, the other in pixels (for example). Third, writing the observation equation in the time variable would make it necessary to predict the transit time for given astrometric, attitude and calibration parameters, which is an inverse calculation and implicitly more complex than the forward calculation of the field angles for a given time.

Formulating the observation equations in the field angles requires that the ‘observed’ along-scan field angle η_ℓ^{obs} is defined as the along-scan field-angle position of the relevant CCD chip and pixel column, *according to the current geometric calibration*, or:

$$\eta_\ell^{\text{obs}} = \eta_n^0 + \Delta\eta_{fnj} + \delta\eta_{nmk} \quad (6)$$

This must then be compared with the field angle calculated from the current astrometric, attitude, and global parameters, *at the observed CCD transit time* t_ℓ^{obs} :

$$\eta_\ell^{\text{calc}} = F_\eta(t_\ell^{\text{obs}}, \mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{g}) \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{a} , \mathbf{q} and \mathbf{g} represent the current astrometric, attitude and global parameters, and $F()$ is a general procedure (PredictedFieldAngles) for computing (η, ζ) at a given time for these parameters. The along-scan residual is, therefore,

$$R_\ell^\eta \equiv \eta_\ell^{\text{obs}} - \eta_\ell^{\text{calc}} = \eta_n^0 + \Delta\eta_{fnj} + \delta\eta_{nmk} - F_\eta(t_\ell^{\text{obs}}, \mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{g}) \quad (8)$$

In the across-scan direction, the observed pixel column coordinate μ is similarly translated into an ‘observed’ transverse field angle ζ_ℓ^{obs} , to be compared with the one predicted from the astrometric, attitude and global parameters. The across-scan residual is, therefore,

$$R_\ell^\zeta \equiv \zeta_\ell^{\text{obs}} - \zeta_\ell^{\text{calc}} = \zeta_n^0 + \Delta\zeta_{fnk} - F_\zeta(t_\ell^{\text{obs}}, \mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{g}) \quad (9)$$

The along- and across-scan residuals are the main input to the estimation process.

2.4 Estimation procedure

In the geometric calibration the values of the predicted field angles returned by F never change and the residuals are linear in the calibration parameters. The latter can therefore be estimated by direct application of the linear least-squares method. The complete design matrix is however very big and connected, since every along-scan observation couples one large-scale and one small-scale parameter. We propose to use a block-iterative solution method similar to GIS, so that $\Delta\eta$ is estimated while ignoring the errors in $\delta\eta$, and vice versa, but without actually iterating the solution. The correct convergence is nevertheless assured thanks to the outer GIS iteration loop.

We are thus able to consider a single calibration parameter p at a time (i.e., one of Δ_{fnj} , δ_{nmk} , or $\Delta\zeta_{fnk}$ for a particular combination of indices f , n , m , j and k), and the weighted average in (36) applies. Since $\partial R_\ell / \partial p = 1$ if p is any of the above calibration parameters affecting observation ℓ , the update to p is obtained as

$$x = -\frac{\sum_\ell R_\ell d(z_\ell) \sigma_\ell^{-2}}{\sum_\ell d(z_\ell) \sigma_\ell^{-2}} \quad (10)$$

where R_ℓ is given by (8) or (9) and $d(z_\ell)$ is the downweighting factor determined in the final internal iteration of the source updating; see Eq. (7) in Lindegren (GAIA-LL-055).

For each calibration parameter p we thus need to accumulate the two sums in (10). This can be done in parallel with the source updating, if all the sums can be kept in primary memory. (Only primary sources should be used.) Having accumulated the sums in (10) for all primary sources, the calibration parameters are updated as $p += x$.

After having updated all the calibration parameters, it remains to enforce the constraints in Sect. 2.2. This is done by first calculating the averages in (3)–(5) for all relevant combinations of indices f , n , j and k , and then subtracting from each parameter the relevant average. Since each parameter is included in exactly one average, the constraints will be satisfied after this operation. The resulting parameters are used for calculating the residuals in the next GIS iteration by means of (8) and (9).

3 Summary of calibration procedure

The geometric calibration can thus be summarized in the following steps:

1. At the start of the GIS loop, the calibration parameters $\Delta\eta_{fnj}$, $\delta\eta_{nmk}$ and $\Delta\zeta_{fnk}$ may be initialized to zero, or they may have the values determined in a previous GIS solution (or from a ground-based calibration). Possibly only some of the parameters need to be initialized (e.g., for a new time interval).
2. Initialize the sums in (10) to zero for every calibration parameter.
3. The sums in (10) are successively accumulated during the source updating. This is done for sources retained as primary sources, using the post-fit residuals R_ℓ^η and R_ℓ^ζ of the source updating, and the corresponding weights $d(z_\ell) \sigma_\ell^{-2}$. (The same residuals and weights are used to accumulate the normal equations for the attitude update.)
4. After completing the source updating, compute the updates from (10) and apply them to the calibration parameters. Do not attempt to update a parameter if the denominator in (10) is zero, meaning that no primary star observation touched that chip or pixel column. Possibly a lower limit for the accumulated weight should be used for the updating to take place.

5. Compute the averages in (3)–(5) and subtract the relevant average from each calibration parameter.
6. Start the next GIS iteration by returning to Step 2. The criterion for breaking the GIS loop will be discussed elsewhere.

4 Extended model

4.1 Extended geometric model

Following Bastian (GAIA-ARI-BAS-011-4) we extend the geometric part of the calibration model by replacing the large-scale AL calibration parameter $\Delta\eta_{fnj}$ with a polynomial function of the normalized across-scan coordinate $\tilde{\mu} = \mu/1966$,

$$\Delta\eta_{fnj}(\tilde{\mu}) = \sum_{r=0}^2 \Delta\eta_{rfnj} L_r^*(\tilde{\mu}) \quad (11)$$

where L_r^* are the shifted Legendre polynomials defined in GAIA-ARI-BAS-011-4. The parameters for $r = 0$ have the same geometrical interpretation as $\Delta\eta_{fnj}$ and must be subject to the same constraints (2a) as before, viz.

$$\langle \Delta\eta_{0fnj} \rangle_j = 0 \quad (\text{for all } j) \quad (12)$$

The higher-order parameters (for $r = 1, 2$) absorb part of the small-scale AL calibration $\delta\eta_{nmk}$, but in contrast to the latter may be different in the two FOVs and may vary on a shorter time scale. However, to ensure a unique separation between the large and small scale parameters, additional constraints have to be introduced for the latter, as described in GAIA-ARI-BAS-011-4. In the present notation they are

$$\langle \delta\eta_{nmk} L_r^*(m/1966) \rangle_{rnk} = 0 \quad (\text{for all } r, n, k) \quad (13)$$

which holds also for $r = 0$, where it replaces (2b).

4.2 Model for magnitude dependent shifts

One of the objectives of the large-scale simulations was to demonstrate the ability of AGIS to solve for the centroid shifts that will result from radiation damage to the CCDs (CTI effects). It is assumed that an empirical or analytical function can be set up describing the shift as function of known variables (magnitude, background, radiation dose, charge injection history, etc). The only remaining unknown to be solved in AGIS is the numerical coefficient to be applied to this function. The coefficient may be different for each CCD, time interval, etc, but should not depend on the FOV index.

The functional form for the shift is not yet known, but it is expected that it will have a strong dependence on the magnitude of the source. Moreover, it is interesting from a theoretical viewpoint to demonstrate that magnitude dependent instrumental shifts can be properly estimated in AGIS, and thus will not propagate into a magnitude dependent reference frame. Thus, as a first approximation we simply assume a linear variation of the centroid shift with magnitude,

$$\Delta\eta^{\text{mag}} = C_{nk}^{\text{mag}}(G - G_{\text{ref}}) \quad (14)$$

where G_{ref} is an arbitrarily chosen reference magnitude, and C_{nk}^{mag} are calibration parameters. $G_{\text{ref}} = 11.0$ mag was used for the simulations (GASS-LSS-1-D/G/H).

4.3 Model for spectrum dependent shifts

Wavefront aberrations introduce a spectrum dependent centroid shift referred to as chromaticity. The shift depends not only on the spectral energy distribution of the source, but also on the details of the centroid definition and estimation (see also Lindegren, LL-068). The chromaticity model used here is based on the finding in de Bruijne et al. (JDB-028) that in practice the centroid position for polychromatic LSFs tends to be roughly a linear function of the effective wavenumber, ν_{eff} . Thus, to first order we model the chromatic displacement as

$$\Delta\eta^{\text{sp}} = C_{f nk}^{\text{sp}}(\nu_{\text{eff}} - \nu_{\text{ref}}) \quad (15)$$

where ν_{ref} is an arbitrarily chosen reference value for the wavenumbers, and $C_{f nk}^{\text{sp}}$ are calibration parameters. $\nu_{\text{ref}} = 1.5 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ was used for the simulations (GASS-LSS-1-E/G/H). The spectrum dependent shift will, in contrast to $\Delta\eta^{\text{mag}}$, also depend on the FOV index, the wavefront aberrations being different in the two FOVs.

4.4 Model synthesis

The complete model for the AL geometry is (cf. Lammers et al., UL-021)

$$\eta_{\ell} = \eta_n^0 + \sum_{r=0}^2 \Delta\eta_{r f n j} L_r^*(\tilde{\mu}_{\ell}) + \delta\eta_{m m k} + C_{nk}^{\text{mag}}(G_{\ell} - G_{\text{ref}}) + C_{f nk}^{\text{sp}}(\nu_{\ell} - \nu_{\text{ref}}) \quad (16)$$

where $\nu_{\ell} = \nu_{\text{eff}\ell}$ for brevity.

5 Correlations among the calibration parameters

Equation (36) gives the formula used for estimating a single calibration parameter p in the basic model described in Sect. 2. Applying the same formula to the estimation of $C_{f nk}^{\text{sp}}$ (for example) gives $\partial R_{\ell}/\partial p = \nu_{\ell} - \nu_{\text{ref}}$ and consequently the update

$$\Delta C_{f nk}^{\text{sp}} = - \frac{\sum_{\ell} R_{\ell} (\nu_{\ell} - \nu_{\text{ref}}) d(z_{\ell}) \sigma_{\ell}^{-2}}{\sum_{\ell} (\nu_{\ell} - \nu_{\text{ref}})^2 d(z_{\ell}) \sigma_{\ell}^{-2}} \quad (17)$$

The first attempts to run AGIS with a calibration model including the estimation of C^{SP} using the above formula³ showed an unexpected oscillatory behaviour between the AL large-scale parameters $\Delta\eta$ and C^{SP} . It was quickly realized that this behaviour was caused by a strong correlation between these two calibration terms resulting from a mismatch between the reference wavenumber $\nu_{\text{ref}} = 1.5 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ (used in both the simulation and and solution) and the actual mean wavenumber $\langle\nu_\ell\rangle \simeq 2.0186 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$. Indeed, running the solution with $\nu_{\text{ref}} = 2.0186 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ eliminated the oscillations and gave rapid convergence to the correct values of C^{SP} , but of course to erroneous $\Delta\eta$ (offset by $0.50186C^{\text{SP}}$). One possible remedy would be to change the reference wavenumber so that it always coincides with the mean wavenumber, but this would be problematic in several respects (e.g., it could mean using different reference values for different data sets). A better solution is to treat the correlations properly (Mantis issue 1461: *spectro-ALLarge correlation*).

5.1 Origin of correlation

To better understand what the correlation means, consider the estimation of just three of the calibration parameters in (16), say $\Delta\eta_{0fnj}$, $\Delta\eta_{1fnj}$, and $C_{f nk}^{\text{SP}}$. Note that they refer to two different calibration units, fnj and $f nk$. The relevant part of the linearized observation equation for the updates, Eq. (35), reads

$$\cdots + L_0^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)\Delta\Delta\eta_{0fnj} + L_1^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)\Delta\Delta\eta_{1fnj} + (\nu_\ell - \nu_{\text{ref}})\Delta C_{f nk}^{\text{SP}} + \cdots \sim R_\ell \quad (18)$$

where $\Delta\Delta\eta_{0fnj}$ is the update to $\Delta\eta_{0fnj}$, etc. Writing $w_\ell = d(z_\ell)\sigma_\ell^{-2}$ for the weight of observation ℓ , we find that the corresponding part of the normal equations has the structure indicated in the table below:

TABLE 2: Structure of the normal equations for three of the calibration parameters.

	$\Delta\eta_{0fnj}$	$\Delta\eta_{1fnj}$	$C_{f nk}^{\text{SP}}$	RHS
$\Delta\eta_{0fnj}$	$[w_\ell L_0^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)^2]$	$[w_\ell L_0^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)L_1^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)]$	$[w_\ell L_0^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)(\nu_\ell - \nu_{\text{ref}})]$	$-[w_\ell L_0^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)R_\ell]$
$\Delta\eta_{1fnj}$	\cdot	$[w_\ell L_1^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)^2]$	$[w_\ell L_1^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)(\nu_\ell - \nu_{\text{ref}})]$	$-[w_\ell L_1^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)R_\ell]$
$C_{f nk}^{\text{SP}}$	\cdot	\cdot	$[w_\ell(\nu_\ell - \nu_{\text{ref}})^2]$	$-[w_\ell(\nu_\ell - \nu_{\text{ref}})R_\ell]$

In this table, the unknowns are listed along the top and left borders of the normal equations matrix, and the right-hand side (RHS) is given along the right border of the matrix. The matrix

³This was CY03-C3 cycle 61 [July 2007], using GASS-LSS-1-E. A previous attempt to process GASS-LSS-1-D, including the magnitude dependent shift, was terminated because the simulated data by mistake contained other effects as well.

is symmetric, and only the upper-diagonal part of the matrix is given explicitly; the symmetric elements below the diagonal are indicated by dots.

The use of square brackets [] in the table is unconventional and requires some explanation. It means ‘summation over the relevant observations’, where ‘relevant’ means referring to the calibration unit or units of the corresponding unknowns. Thus, the matrix element $[w_\ell L_0^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)^2]$ is obtained by a summation over all observations ℓ referring to calibration unit fnj , the matrix element $[w_\ell L_0^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)(\nu_\ell - \nu_{\text{ref}})]$ is obtained by a summation over all observations that refer to both calibration unit fnj and fnk , and the RHS element $-[w_\ell(\nu_\ell - \nu_{\text{ref}})R_\ell]$ is obtained by a summation over all the observations that refer to calibration unit fnk . Note that the same bracketed expression would mean different things depending on its position in the table, since the row and column determines the scope of the summation.

The correlations that are of concern to us here are caused by non-negligible off-diagonal elements in the normal equations matrix. If the off-diagonal elements are negligible (in comparison with the diagonal elements), each line of the equations can be solved independently; e.g. from the first normal equation in Table 2 we get the solution for the update to $\Delta\eta_{0fnj}$ simply as

$$\Delta\Delta\eta_{0fnj} = \frac{-[w_\ell L_0^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)R_\ell]}{[w_\ell L_0^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)^2]} \quad (19)$$

which (recalling that $L_0^*(x) = 1$) is the same as (10). Again by neglecting the off-diagonal elements, we similarly get from the third line an update to C_{fnk}^{sp} according to (17).

In the extended geometric calibration model, all the calibration parameters are either uncorrelated by design, or the correlations that are known to exist (e.g., between the large-scale and the small-scale parameters) are handled by means of the constraints. Parameters that refer to separate calibration units (different CCDs, or non-overlapping time intervals) are of course always uncorrelated, since they have no observations in common and therefore the corresponding bracket is strictly zero.

To understand what is meant by ‘uncorrelated by design’, let us have a closer look at the off-diagonal entries in Table 2. The matrix element $[w_\ell L_0^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)L_1^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)]$ is a sum over the observations in calibration unit fnj . It is reasonable to assume that the $\tilde{\mu}$ values of these observations are very nearly uniformly distributed in the allowed interval $[0, 1]$. Thanks to the orthogonality of the polynomials $L_0^*(\tilde{\mu})$ and $L_1^*(\tilde{\mu})$ on $[0, 1]$ it follows that this matrix element will be negligible, at least as long as w_ℓ does not depend systematically on $\tilde{\mu}$ (and we have no special reason to suspect such a dependence, since w_ℓ depends mainly on the magnitude of the star). Indeed, if w_ℓ and $\tilde{\mu}_\ell$ are uncorrelated, we have $[w_\ell L_0^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)L_1^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)] = [w_\ell]\langle L_0^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)L_1^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)\rangle = 0$. Thus, the coefficients for $\Delta\eta_{0fnj}$ and $\Delta\eta_{1fnj}$ are uncorrelated by design.

Considering next the term $[w_\ell L_1^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)(\nu_\ell - \nu_{\text{ref}})]$, we can infer that this, too, will be negligible since there is no reason to expect a correlation between ν_ℓ and $\tilde{\mu}_\ell$; thus $[w_\ell L_1^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)(\nu_\ell - \nu_{\text{ref}})] = [w_\ell(\nu_\ell - \nu_{\text{ref}})]\langle L_1^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)\rangle = 0$, since $\langle L_1^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)\rangle = 0$ if $\tilde{\mu}_\ell$ has a uniform distribution in $[0, 1]$.

The situation is however different for the third off-diagonal term, which under the same assumption becomes $[w_\ell L_0^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell)(\nu_\ell - \nu_{\text{ref}})] = [w_\ell(\nu_\ell - \nu_{\text{ref}})]\langle L_0^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell) \rangle = [w_\ell(\nu_\ell - \nu_{\text{ref}})] \neq 0$, since we have seen that $\langle \nu_\ell \rangle \neq \nu_{\text{ref}}$.

5.2 Solution for two correlated parameters in the same calibration unit

In the Appendix the estimation of a single parameter p is considered, which is fine as long as it is essentially uncorrelated with other parameters. Let us now consider the estimation of two correlated parameters p and q that refer to the same calibration unit. The linearized observation equation for the updates Δp , Δq derived from (35) reads

$$a_\ell \Delta p + b_\ell \Delta q \sim R_\ell \quad (20)$$

where $a_\ell = -\partial R_\ell / \partial p$ and $b_\ell = -\partial R_\ell / \partial q$. As before we use w_ℓ for the weight of the observation and use square brackets to denote a sum over all the observations in the calibration unit. The normal equations are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} [w_\ell a_\ell^2] \Delta p + [w_\ell a_\ell b_\ell] \Delta q &= [w_\ell a_\ell R_\ell] \\ [w_\ell a_\ell b_\ell] \Delta p + [w_\ell b_\ell^2] \Delta q &= [w_\ell b_\ell R_\ell] \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (21)$$

with the explicit solution

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta p &= \frac{[w_\ell b_\ell^2][w_\ell a_\ell R_\ell] - [w_\ell a_\ell b_\ell][w_\ell b_\ell R_\ell]}{[w_\ell a_\ell^2][w_\ell b_\ell^2] - [w_\ell a_\ell b_\ell]^2} \\ \Delta q &= \frac{[w_\ell a_\ell^2][w_\ell b_\ell R_\ell] - [w_\ell a_\ell b_\ell][w_\ell a_\ell R_\ell]}{[w_\ell a_\ell^2][w_\ell b_\ell^2] - [w_\ell a_\ell b_\ell]^2} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (22)$$

Anticipating the generalization discussed in Sect. 5.3, we shall re-write the solution (22) in a slightly curious form. Introduce the auxiliary quantity

$$\beta = \frac{[w_\ell a_\ell b_\ell]}{[w_\ell a_\ell^2]} \quad (23)$$

which is the regression coefficient of b_ℓ on a_ℓ , i.e., the least-squares estimate of the coefficient in $b_\ell \sim \beta a_\ell$. We have $\beta = 0$ if and only if the two parameters are uncorrelated. The solution can now be written

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta p^{(\text{prov})} &= \frac{[w_\ell a_\ell R_\ell]}{[w_\ell a_\ell^2]} \\ \Delta q &= \frac{[w_\ell b_\ell R_\ell] - \beta [w_\ell a_\ell^2] \Delta p^{(\text{prov})}}{[w_\ell b_\ell^2] - \beta^2 [w_\ell a_\ell^2]} \\ \Delta p &= \Delta p^{(\text{prov})} - \beta \Delta q \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (24)$$

$\Delta p^{(\text{prov})}$ is the ('provisional') solution for Δp obtained by neglecting the correlation with q . The remaining equations give the exact solution in terms of the provisional solution and β .

FIGURE 1: Visualization of the grouped calibration parameters considered in Sect. 5.3. The boxes show the range of observations (ℓ) covered by the different calibration units. Let $\mathcal{L}(q)$ denote the set of observations for which the parameter q applies. Then for a valid grouping we must have $\mathcal{L}(q) = \cup_g \mathcal{L}(p_g)$ and $\mathcal{L}(p_g) \cap \mathcal{L}(p_{g'}) = \emptyset$ for $g \neq g'$.

5.3 Solution for grouped parameters

The solution (24) cannot be directly applied to the case of the magnitude or spectrum dependent shifts being correlated with the the large-scale AL calibration parameter, since the parameters belong to calibration units that overlap but do not coincide. In this section we generalize the result to the case of ‘grouped’ parameters. The meaning of this concept is illustrated in Fig. 1: a group of parameters p_g (where g is the group index) cover exactly the same observations as the parameter q . The observation equation for observation ℓ belonging to group g is

$$a_\ell \Delta p_g + b_\ell \Delta q \sim R_\ell \quad (25)$$

The normal equations become:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \forall g : \quad [w_\ell a_\ell^2]_g \Delta p_g + [w_\ell a_\ell b_\ell]_g \Delta q &= [w_\ell a_\ell R_\ell]_g \\ \sum_g [w_\ell a_\ell b_\ell]_g \Delta p_g + [w_\ell b_\ell^2] \Delta q &= [w_\ell b_\ell R_\ell] \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (26)$$

where $[]_g$ means summation over the observations in group g , while $[]$ as before means summation over all the observations, i.e., for all groups. This system has the block-angular structure and can be solved by the well-known Helmert blocking method (here trivially applied to blocks of dimension 1, which is in fact a straightforward application of gaussian elimination). After elimination of the unknowns Δp_g , we are left with a reduced system for Δq which is easily solved, after which each Δp_g is obtained by back-substitution. In analogy with (24) we find that this can be written in the following form:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \forall g : \quad \Delta p_g^{(\text{prov})} &= \frac{[w_\ell a_\ell R_\ell]_g}{[w_\ell a_\ell^2]_g}, \quad \beta_g = \frac{[w_\ell a_\ell b_\ell]_g}{[w_\ell a_\ell^2]_g} \\ \Delta q &= \frac{[w_\ell b_\ell R_\ell] - \sum_g \beta_g [w_\ell a_\ell^2]_g \Delta p_g^{(\text{prov})}}{[w_\ell b_\ell^2] - \sum_g \beta_g^2 [w_\ell a_\ell^2]_g} \\ \forall g : \quad \Delta p_g &= \Delta p_g^{(\text{prov})} - \beta_g \Delta q \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (27)$$

5.4 Application to the magnitude and spectrum dependent shifts

The solution method (27) was implemented in AGIS R_3.0 (Lammers. U., UL-029) to separately cope with the two cases:

1. the correlation between the magnitude dependent shift C_{nk}^{mag} and the AL large-scale calibration $\Delta\eta_{fnj}$ (or $\Delta\eta_{0fnj}$ in the extended geometric calibration model); and
2. the correlation between the spectrum dependent shift C_{fnk}^{sp} and the AL large-scale calibration $\Delta\eta_{fnj}$ (or $\Delta\eta_{0fnj}$ in the extended geometric calibration model).

In Case 1 the groups consist of the different combinations of f and j that make up a given k (with separate solutions for each n), and the coefficients are $a_\ell = -L_0^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell) = -1$ and $b_\ell = -(G - G_{\text{ref}})$. This was successfully tested on the data set GASS-LSS-1-E (Luri & Babusiaux, XL-004) in AGIS CY03-C2 (Bach et al., NB-002).

In Case 2 the groups are the different possible values of j for given k (with separate solutions for each combination of f and n), and the coefficients are $a_\ell = -L_0^*(\tilde{\mu}_\ell) = -1$ and $b_\ell = -(\nu_\ell - \nu_{\text{ref}})$. This was successfully tested on the data set GASS-LSS-1-D (Luri & Babusiaux, XL-004) in AGIS CY03-C1 (Bach et al., NB-001).

The test runs described above did not include the extended geometric calibration model (only the zero-order terms $\Delta\eta_{fnj}$); the extended model – without spectrum and magnitude dependent shifts – was separately tested on GASS-LSS-1-F (Luri & Babusiaux, XL-004) in AGIS CY03-C3 (Bach & Lammers, NB-003). The additional data set GASS-LSS-1-G combining the extended geometric model with spectrum and magnitude dependent shifts (and a variation of the basic angle) could not be processed with AGIS R_3.0 since the solution method described here cannot cope with three mutually correlated sets of calibration parameters.

6 Conclusions

With the inclusion of the extended geometric calibration model and the spectrum and magnitude dependent shifts, the calibration model has grown substantially in complexity and a new type of solution had to be implemented to cope with the correlations that now occur between some of the parameters. This allowed the magnitude *or* spectrum dependent shifts to be solved simultaneously with the AL large-scale calibration, assuming a certain structure of the calibration units (Fig. 1). However, if *both* magnitude and spectrum dependent shifts are simultaneously present, they cannot be solved by this method without further, non-trivial modification. At this point it was concluded that a better approach will be to develop a generic calibration model that allows to take into account multiple correlations in a more general way (Lammers, UL-031).

7 References

- Bach, N., Lammers, U., 2008, *AGIS Validation Test Report of CY03-C3*,
GAIA-C3-TR-ESAC-NB-003,
URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/2811474>
- Bach, N., Raison, F., Lammers, U., 2008, *AGIS Validation Test Report of CY03-C1*,
GAIA-C3-TR-ESAC-NB-001,
URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/2809823>
- Bach, N., Raison, F., Lammers, U., 2008, *AGIS Validation Test Report of CY03-C2*,
GAIA-C3-TR-ESAC-NB-002,
URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/2809930>
- Bastian, U., 2006, *Extended geometric calibration model for Gaia's Astro instrument*,
GAIA-ARI-BAS-011-4,
URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/420453>
- Bastian, U., 2007, *Reference systems, conventions and notations for Gaia*,
GAIA-CA-SP-ARI-BAS-003,
URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/358698>
- de Bruijne, J., Lindegren, L., Svensson, O., et al., 2006, *Chromaticity in Gaia-3*,
GAIA-CA-TN-ESA-JDB-028,
URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/2694426>
- Lammers, U., 2008, *Proposal of a Generic Astrometric Calibration Scheme for the Data Processing*,
GAIA-C3-TN-ESAC-UL-031,
URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/2817459>
- Lammers, U., Lindegren, L., O'Mullane, W., et al., 2006, *Simulation Requirements for AGIS Development Cycles 1 and 2*,
GAIA-C3-SP-ESAC-UL-021,
URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/2695195>
- Lammers, U., 2007, *AGIS 3.0 Software Release Note*,
GAIA-C3-SP-ESAC-UL-029,
URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/2774107>
- Lindegren, L., 2001, *Global Iterative Solution - Distributed processing of the attitude updating*,
SAG-LL-037,
URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/357816>

Lindgren, L., 2003, *Algorithms for GDAAS Phase II - Definition*,

GAIA-LL-044,

URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/357790>

Lindgren, L., 2004, *A proposed new algorithm for source updating*,

GAIA-LL-055,

URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/390988>

Lindgren, L., 2006, *Centroid definition for the Astro line spread function*,

GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-068,

URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/2698669>

Luri, X., Babusiaux, C., 2007, *Consolidated list of simulation requirements and CU2 planning for cycle 3*,

GAIA-C2-SP-UB-XL-004,

URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/2760525>

A Appendix: Some least-squares terminology and conventions

The generic form of an observation equation (or equation of condition) in the variable ϕ (such as one of the field angles) resulting from an observation ℓ , is:

$$\phi_\ell^{\text{calc}}(\mathbf{p}) \sim \phi_\ell^{\text{obs}} \quad (\pm\sigma_\ell) \quad (28)$$

where ϕ^{calc} is a known function of the unknown parameters \mathbf{p} , ϕ^{obs} is the observed value of the variable, and ‘ \sim ’ means ‘equals, apart from a noise term which we think has standard deviation σ_ℓ ’. Each observation ℓ generates an observation equation of this form.

In least-squares estimation, a set of observation equations are processed to give an estimate of \mathbf{p} (often denoted $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$) and its covariance matrix, $\text{Cov}(\hat{\mathbf{p}})$. In principle the estimation is done by minimizing the sum of squared normalized residuals, $\sum_\ell (R_\ell/\sigma_\ell)^2$, where

$$R_\ell = \phi_\ell^{\text{obs}} - \phi_\ell^{\text{calc}}(\mathbf{p}) \quad (29)$$

Note that residuals are always defined in the sense ‘observed *minus* calculated’ (or ‘actual value *minus* predicted value’).

In the general case the function ϕ^{calc} is highly non-linear in the unknowns \mathbf{p} , but we usually have a reasonably good initial estimate \mathbf{p}_0 , so we can linearize (28) by means of the first-order Taylor expansion

$$\phi_\ell^{\text{calc}}(\mathbf{p}_0 + \mathbf{x}) = \phi_\ell^{\text{calc}}(\mathbf{p}_0) + \left(\frac{\partial \phi_\ell^{\text{calc}}}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \right)_{\mathbf{p}_0} \cdot \mathbf{x} + O(|\mathbf{x}|^2) \quad (30)$$

Neglecting higher-order terms and moving the zero-order term to the right hand side gives the linearized observation equation

$$\left(\frac{\partial \phi_\ell^{\text{calc}}}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \right)_{\mathbf{p}_0} \cdot \mathbf{x} \sim \phi_\ell^{\text{obs}} - \phi_\ell^{\text{calc}}(\mathbf{p}_0) \quad (\pm\sigma_\ell) \quad (31)$$

The right hand side consists of the residuals with respect to the initial estimate \mathbf{p}_0 , which we may call the pre-fit residuals. The aim is to minimize the post-fit residuals. Equation (31) is linear in the unknowns \mathbf{x} and the minimization problem is then easily solved by the use of normal equations, orthogonal transformations, SVD, or any other suitable numerical algorithm (cf. Lindegren, GAIA-LL-055). Updating the parameter vector gives the improved estimate

$$\mathbf{p}_1 = \mathbf{p}_0 + \mathbf{x} \quad (32)$$

If the higher-order terms in (30) are significant, it will be necessary to iterate the least-squares process by calculating new residuals with respect to \mathbf{p}_1 , solving again for \mathbf{x} , and apply the

updating to get p_2 , etc. The iteration continues until $|x|$ is negligible at which point we have converged to the final parameter vector \hat{p} .⁴ The post-fit residuals

$$\hat{R}_\ell = \phi_\ell^{\text{obs}} - \phi_\ell^{\text{calc}}(\hat{p}) \quad (33)$$

are used to calculate various statistics, and as input to other algorithms.

The least-squares processing must handle simultaneously all the observation equations of the form (31) that depend on the parameters p being updated. Since the equations are linear, they can be expressed in matrix form as

$$\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{x} \sim \mathbf{b} \pm \boldsymbol{\sigma} \quad (34)$$

where the dimensions of \mathbf{A} are $N \times \dim(p)$, if N is the number of observations considered; \mathbf{b} and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ are column matrices of length N containing the current residuals and observational uncertainties. Each row of (34) thus corresponds to one observation. \mathbf{A} is variously referred to as the observation equations matrix, the coefficient matrix, or the design matrix. For the further treatment of (34), including observation weighting and the formation and solution of normal equations, refer to Lindegren (GAIA-LL-055).

For the Gaia calibration updating we have the somewhat unorthodox situation that the calibration parameters are included in the *observed* field angles, not in the *computed* values. Application of (31) as it stands will not work, since the partial derivatives of ϕ^{calc} with respect to the calibration parameters are strictly zero. We solve this formal problem by a slight reformulation of the linearized observation equation. Since the objective of the least-squares estimation is to minimize the residuals, it obviously does not matter whether the updating affects ϕ^{obs} or ϕ^{calc} , as long as the effect on the residuals is the same. Thus we should simply replace $\partial\phi^{\text{calc}}/\partial p$ by $-\partial R/\partial p$, which will work in either case. The more general form of the linearized observation equation in iteration i is, therefore,

$$\left(-\frac{\partial R_\ell}{\partial p} \right)_{p_i} \cdot \mathbf{x} \sim R_\ell \equiv \phi_\ell^{\text{obs}} - \phi_\ell^{\text{calc}}(p_i) \quad (\pm\sigma_\ell) \quad (35)$$

In the special case when p is one-dimensional, the least-squares solution of (34) reduces to computing a weighted average of the product of the derivatives and residuals. Using (35) we find

$$x = \frac{\sum_\ell (-\partial R_\ell/\partial p) R_\ell \sigma_\ell^{-2}}{\sum_\ell (-\partial R_\ell/\partial p)^2 \sigma_\ell^{-2}} \quad (36)$$

followed by the updating $p += x$.

⁴In this process it may or may not be necessary to recompute $\partial\phi^{\text{calc}}/\partial p$ in each iteration, depending on the degree of non-linearity. Although the iteration process normally converges even if the partial derivatives are slightly wrong (although a bit slower), it is good practice to recompute the derivatives at least when p is close to the converged value, or after convergence has been established. In any case, the right-hand side of (31) must always be recomputed in each iteration.